

Dissociation Constants of Acetic Acid in Methanol-Water Media at Different Temperatures and Related Thermodynamic Quantities

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Dissociation constants of acetic acid in methanol-water media containing 30, 45, 60, 75 and 90% by weight of methanol at 15, 20, 25, 30 and 35° have been determined using the cell

At any temperature, the pK_a increases as the solvent becomes enriched in methanol. In media with any particular composition, pK_a over the temperature range passes through a minimum. ΔG° , ΔH° , ΔS° and ΔC_p° for the dissociation process at 25° have been calculated.

In our programme¹⁻³ to determine the standard potentials of $\text{Hg, Hg}_2 - \text{X}_2/\text{X}^-$, where X^- is acetate or propionate ion, for the standard potentials of mercury/mercurous acetate electrode in dioxane-water, and mercury/mercurous propionate electrodes in water and dioxane-water media, we used the values of the dissociation constants of acetic acid and propionic acid in the respective media as reported by Harned and coworkers⁴⁻⁸. While extending the determination in methanol-water media we found that the dissociation constants over a wide range of solvent-composition and temperature are not available in the literature. Harned and Embree⁹ determined the values of K_a only in 10 and 20% of methanol at different temperatures. Bacarella *et al.*¹⁰ determined the pK values in methanol-water media at 25° using glass electrode and Shedlovsky and Kay¹¹ by conductometric method. Recently, Paabo, Robinson and Bates¹² determined the values of pK over a temperature range of 10-40° but only in 50% methanol. In this communication we report the dissociation constants of acetic acid in 30, 45, 60, 75 and 90% by weight of methanol and at 15, 20, 25, 30 and 35°.

Experimental

Methanol (A.R., B.D.H.) was refluxed with iodine and sodium hydroxide and then distilled. The distillate was further refluxed with Zn-dust and KOH and subsequently distilled. The middle fraction was collected for use. The methods for the purification of acetic acid, the preparation of hydrogen electrode and the cell set-up have been described in our previous communication¹.

The silver-silver chloride electrodes used are of thermal electrolytic type and have been prepared by

the method recommended by Bates¹³. Cells of the type similar to that used by Harned and Ehlers¹⁴,

have been used in the present measurements. We have used buffered solutions in the cell since the errors¹⁵⁻¹⁹ that vitiate the dissociation constants of polybasic acids from the use of buffered solutions because of ion association of poly-valent anions, does not arise in the case of acetic acid. The measurements have been taken at five temperatures, 15, 20, 25, 30 and 35° with a Leeds-Northrup K_a potentiometer and galvanometer, the cell e.m.f. values being measured first from 25 to 35° and then from 15 to 25°. The measured e.m.f. readings have been corrected to that for the standard 1 atmosphere pressure of hydrogen using the expression¹⁴,

$$\Delta E = 2.3026 \frac{RT}{2F} \log \frac{760}{(P - P_s)}$$

where P = barometric pressure, and P_s = vapour pressure of the solvent.

The vapour pressures of methanol-water systems at different temperatures and of different compositions have been taken from the work of Harned and coworkers²⁰ and Melton and Amis²¹. The corrected e.m.f. values for the cell presented in Table 1 are the average of four sets. The e.m.f. values at 25° at the first and at the last readings were in good agreement (always <0.05 mV) and their values are the average of eight readings.

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TABLE 1—E.m.f. VALUES OF CELL (E/V) CORRECTED TO 1 ATM PRESSURE OF H₂ AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Pt, H ₂ (g) HOAc(m ₁), NaOAc(m ₂), NaCl(m ₃) AgCl, Ag		Temperature °C				
methanol (X%), water (100-X) %						
m ₁	m ₂ =m ₃	15	20	25	30	35
30% Methanol						
0.5189	0.0915	0.52022	0.52344	0.52655	0.52980	0.53201
0.4985	0.0879	0.52141	0.52459	0.52767	0.53041	0.53311
0.4679	0.0826	0.52332	0.52646	0.52950	0.53224	0.53493
0.4371	0.0771	0.52523	0.52834	0.53135	0.53406	0.53675
0.4065	0.0717	0.52731	0.53039	0.53336	0.53607	0.53875
0.3937	0.0436	0.52949	0.53231	0.53496	0.53748	0.53996
0.3518	0.0390	0.53245	0.53528	0.53792	0.54046	0.54295
0.2678	0.0297	0.53976	0.54259	0.54524	0.54783	0.55037
0.2471	0.0274	0.54187	0.54471	0.54737	0.54997	0.55254
0.2263	0.0251	0.54418	0.54708	0.54970	0.55232	0.55491
45% Methanol						
0.5554	0.0615	0.52962	0.53234	0.53502	0.53771	0.53998
0.4804	0.0532	0.53407	0.53678	0.53946	0.54217	0.54395
0.3964	0.0439	0.53979	0.54241	0.54501	0.54748	0.54964
0.3546	0.0393	0.54298	0.54556	0.54816	0.55060	0.55283
0.3128	0.0347	0.54662	0.54919	0.55178	0.55425	0.55650
0.1925	0.0309	0.57027	0.57320	0.57614	0.57900	0.58162
0.1106	0.0288	0.57298	0.57592	0.57887	0.58176	0.58442
0.0989	0.0249	0.57622	0.57916	0.58211	0.58502	0.58770
0.0750	0.0189	0.58369	0.58665	0.58965	0.59265	0.59541
0.0632	0.0159	0.58839	0.59138	0.59442	0.59747	0.60030
60% Methanol						
0.3309	0.0957	0.54486	0.54778	0.55078	0.55366	0.55678
0.3095	0.0895	0.54735	0.55020	0.55315	0.55601	0.55909
0.2899	0.0821	0.55049	0.55326	0.55615	0.55900	0.56202
0.2582	0.0747	0.55378	0.55647	0.55931	0.56215	0.56512
0.2326	0.0673	0.55742	0.56004	0.56283	0.56565	0.56859
0.2072	0.0599	0.56128	0.56382	0.56658	0.56941	0.57229
0.1816	0.0525	0.56555	0.56803	0.57076	0.57359	0.57644
0.1562	0.0452	0.57038	0.57282	0.57551	0.57836	0.58119
0.1044	0.0302	0.58226	0.58468	0.58731	0.59023	0.59304
0.0789	0.0228	0.59021	0.59258	0.59529	0.59828	0.60112
75% Methanol						
0.2095	0.0606	0.56393	0.56660	0.57013	0.57276	0.57541
0.1772	0.0571	0.56889	0.57162	0.57501	0.57767	0.58036
0.1656	0.0534	0.57144	0.57401	0.57740	0.58004	0.58274
0.1481	0.0478	0.57558	0.57803	0.58128	0.58390	0.58662
0.1364	0.0440	0.57846	0.58083	0.58399	0.58661	0.58933
0.1188	0.0383	0.58321	0.58547	0.58849	0.59109	0.59384
0.1014	0.0327	0.58843	0.59059	0.59350	0.59610	0.59888
0.0898	0.0290	0.59226	0.59436	0.59719	0.59981	0.60261
0.0782	0.0252	0.59665	0.59871	0.60147	0.60410	0.60694
0.0668	0.0216	0.60137	0.60339	0.60610	0.60876	0.61164
90% Methanol						
0.0732	0.0236	0.60245	0.60541	0.60907	0.61235	0.61602
0.0684	0.0221	0.60462	0.60743	0.61104	0.61429	0.61790
0.0661	0.0213	0.60594	0.60875	0.61226	0.61548	0.61908
0.0589	0.0190	0.60973	0.61240	0.61577	0.61895	0.62247
0.0481	0.0155	0.61620	0.61866	0.62181	0.62494	0.62837
0.0408	0.0132	0.62123	0.62357	0.62660	0.62970	0.63308
0.0344	0.0111	0.62640	0.62864	0.63157	0.63466	0.63800
0.0252	0.0081	0.63529	0.63740	0.64021	0.64330	0.64663
0.0194	0.0063	0.64248	0.64456	0.64732	0.65046	0.65380
0.0134	0.0043	0.65252	0.65458	0.65734	0.66055	0.66395

 TABLE 2—VALUES OF $-\log K'_A$ AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Ionic strength	Temperature, °C				
	15	20	25	30	35
30% Methanol					
0.1830	5.1655	5.1738	5.1843	5.1942	5.2066
0.1758	5.1689	5.1762	5.1859	5.1954	5.2073
0.1652	5.1748	5.1808	5.1894	5.1982	5.2095
0.1542	5.1786	5.1836	5.1910	5.1990	5.2096
0.1434	5.1834	5.1872	5.1935	5.2008	5.2108
0.0872	5.2076	5.2063	5.2066	5.2103	5.2167
0.0780	5.2106	5.2085	5.2078	5.2109	5.2167
0.0594	5.2201	5.2158	5.2131	5.2150	5.2197
0.0548	5.2220	5.2174	5.2142	5.2158	5.2202
0.0502	5.2241	5.2189	5.2153	5.2165	5.2207
45% Methanol					
0.1230	5.5118	5.5221	5.5329	5.5418	5.5508
0.1064	5.5267	5.5346	5.5434	5.5508	5.5598
0.0878	5.5433	5.5487	5.5553	5.5615	5.5689
0.0786	5.5506	5.5546	5.5601	5.5658	5.5726
0.0694	5.5598	5.5628	5.5669	5.5721	5.5783
0.0618	5.5666	5.5688	5.5718	5.5765	5.5822
0.0576	5.5694	5.5705	5.5734	5.5779	5.5834
0.0498	5.5774	5.5774	5.5794	5.5834	5.5884
0.0378	5.5881	5.5864	5.5870	5.5903	5.5946
0.0318	5.5955	5.5930	5.5928	5.5957	5.5997
60% Methanol					
0.1914	5.6940	5.7211	5.7444	5.7644	5.7981
0.1790	5.7085	5.7337	5.7554	5.7745	5.8069
0.1643	5.7259	5.7478	5.7686	5.7866	5.8173
0.1494	5.7422	5.7627	5.7808	5.7977	5.8267
0.1346	5.7605	5.7787	5.7950	5.8108	5.8382
0.1198	5.7778	5.7936	5.8082	5.8230	5.8486
0.1050	5.7951	5.8086	5.8214	5.8351	5.8590
0.0904	5.8142	5.8254	5.8364	5.8490	5.8713
0.0604	5.8473	5.8598	5.8612	5.8716	5.8904
0.0456	5.8646	5.8688	5.8743	5.8837	5.9009
75% Methanol					
0.1212	6.1451	6.1801	6.2220	6.2489	6.2750
0.1142	6.1690	6.1919	6.2316	6.2577	6.2832
0.1068	6.1744	6.2053	6.2427	6.2678	6.2928
0.0956	6.1982	6.2258	6.2597	6.2835	6.3077
0.0880	6.2129	6.2394	6.2699	6.2928	6.3164
0.0766	6.2360	6.2581	6.2860	6.3074	6.3302
0.0654	6.2588	6.2776	6.3021	6.3221	6.3440
0.0580	6.2728	6.2896	6.3117	6.3309	6.3522
0.0504	6.2893	6.3039	6.3236	6.3418	6.3626
0.0432	6.3040	6.3165	6.3340	6.3513	6.3715
90% Methanol					
0.0472	7.0557	7.0928	7.1368	7.1787	7.2219
0.0442	7.0645	7.0992	7.1409	7.1767	7.2235
0.0426	7.0722	7.1057	7.1462	7.1812	7.2274
0.0380	7.0887	7.1186	7.1556	7.1890	7.2330
0.0310	7.1138	7.1382	7.1698	7.2006	7.2415
0.0264	7.1303	7.1511	7.1792	7.2082	7.2470
0.0222	7.1474	7.1648	7.1898	7.2172	7.2541
0.0162	7.1669	7.1796	7.2000	7.2251	7.2594
0.0126	7.1798	7.1897	7.2074	7.2311	7.2637
0.0086	7.1942	7.2009	7.2155	7.2377	7.2686

Results and Discussion

The e.m.f. of the cell (1) is related to the concentration of hydrogen ion, m_H , and that of chloride ion, m_{Cl} , by the equation (1).

$$E = E^\circ - \frac{RT}{F} \ln m_H m_{Cl} \gamma_H \gamma_{Cl} \quad (1)$$

where E° is the standard potential of Ag, AgCl electrode and γ_H and γ_{Cl} are the activity coefficients of hydrogen and chloride ions, respectively. The standard potential of silver, silver chloride electrode has been taken from the work of Harned and coworkers²⁰ and Austin *et al.*²². In the equation (1), $m_H \gamma_H$ may be eliminated by introducing the expression for the dissociation constant of acetic acid

which is expressed as in equation (2).

$$K_a = \frac{m_H m_{OAc}}{m_{HOAc}} \frac{\gamma_H \gamma_{OAc}}{\gamma_{HOAc}} \quad (2)$$

$$[HOAc \rightleftharpoons H + OAc]$$

The equation then reduces to equation (3).

$$\frac{(E - E^0)F}{2.3026 RT} + \log \frac{m_{Cl} m_{HOAc}}{m_{OAc}} = -\log k_a - \log \frac{\gamma_{Cl} \gamma_{HOAc}}{\gamma_{OAc}} \quad (3)$$

Now, the molalities of the ionic and unionised are given as,

$$m_{Cl} = m_s = \text{molality of NaCl,}$$

$$m_{HOAc} = m_1 - m_H,$$

and $m_{OAc} = m_2 + m_H$ ($m_2 =$ molality of sodium acetate).

With the assumptions, (i) m_H , the molality of hydrogen ion from the dissociation of acetic acid being of the order of $K_a(m_1/m_2)$ is negligible as compared to m_2 and m_1 , and (ii) the activity of the two uni-valent ions, namely γ_{OAc} and γ_{Cl} , are the same and as such cancel each in the equation (3), the equation (3) may be written in the form

$$\frac{(E - E^0)F}{2.3026 RT} + \log \frac{m_1 m_2}{m_s} = \log K_a - \log \gamma_{HOAc} \quad (4)$$

Long and McDevit²³ have discussed that for buffer solutions the effect of salt on the activity coefficient of acetic acid or any molecular species can be represented by equation (5).

$$\log \gamma_{HOAc} = SI \quad (5)$$

where I is the ionic strength of the solution and S is known as salting coefficient.

Thus, we have

$$\frac{(E - E^0)F}{2.3026 RT} + \log \frac{m_1 m_2}{m_s} = -\log K_a = SI \quad (6)$$

The left hand side of equation (6) is denoted by $\log K'_a$. From the equation, it is apparent that the plot of $\log K'_a$ against the ionic strength, I, is linear and the intercept at the zero ionic strength gives $\log K_a$ and hence K_a , the thermodynamic dissociation constant.

The values of pK_a in methanol-water media of different ionic strengths (column 3) at 15, 20, 25, 30 and 35° are given in columns 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8, respectively. Column 3 of Table 3 presents the thermodynamic dissociation constant (pK_a).

The values of pK_a have been fitted to the equation²⁴

$$pK_a = A^*/T - D^* + C^*T \quad (7)$$

where T is the Kelvin temperature using the method of least squares.

With $\log K_a$ expressed in the form of equation (7) we have the thermodynamic quantities, ΔG^0 , the Gibbs' free energy change, ΔH^0 , the enthalpy change, ΔS^0 , the entropy change, and ΔC_p^0 , the heat

capacity change for the dissociation process by standard procedure in the following forms.

$$\Delta G^0 = 2.303 RT pK_a$$

$$\Delta H^0 = 2.3026 RA^* - 2.3026 KC^* T^2$$

$$\Delta C_p^0 = -2 \times 2.3026 RC^* T$$

$$\text{and } \Delta S^0 = 2.3026 RD^* - \Delta C_p^0.$$

Columns 4, 5, 6 and 7 present the ΔG^0 , ΔS^0 , ΔH^0 and ΔC_p^0 , respectively for the ionisation process at 25°. The quantities for 20, 30 and 50% methanol from literature have also been incorporated (Table 3).

TABLE 3— pK_a VALUES AND RELATED THERMODYNAMIC QUANTITIES FOR DISSOCIATION OF ACETIC ACID IN METHANOL-WATER MEDIA AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Solvent % Methanol	Temp. °C	pK_a	ΔG^0 cal mol ⁻¹	ΔS^0 cal mol ⁻¹ deg ⁻¹	ΔH^0 cal mol ⁻¹	ΔC_p^0 cal mol ⁻¹
0	25	4.772	6486	-22.1	-92	-36.5 ^a
		4.774	6488	-22.1	-95	-37 ^b
	10	4.923	6690	-22.3	30	-43.3 ^a
	20	5.098	6929	-22.7	108	-47.1 ^a
	30	5.246				
45	20	5.236				
	25	5.227	7130	-22.5	407.9	-52.2
	30	5.225				
	35	5.226				
	15	5.622				
50	20	5.615				
	25	5.611	7654	-25.0	144.0	-54.7
	30	5.612				
	35	5.614				
	25	5.6600	7721	-26.2	-52	-54 ^b
60	15	5.918				
	20	5.915				
	25	5.915	8069	-28.1	-302.5	-65.5
	30	5.921				
	35	5.933				
75	15	6.393				
	20	6.392				
	25	6.396	8725	-31.5	-663.5	-86.3
	30	6.408				
	35	6.425				
90	15	7.225				
	20	7.225				
	25	7.233	9867	-36.8	-1115.3	-127.0
	30	7.252				
	35	7.279				

^a Ref. 25, ^b Ref. 28.

The pK_a values of acetic acid at all the five temperatures increase as the proportion of the organic component in the medium increases, similar to the observations reported by us and also others for the variation of pK_a of acids of the type HA ($HA \rightarrow H^+ + A^-$) with change in the dielectric constant of the aquo-organic media²⁶. For any composition of the medium, the pK_a values over the temperature range pass through a minimum²⁴. For 90% methanol medium, the minimum is possibly at temperature lower than 15°. Ionisation of natural molecules into charged species according to Frank and Evans²⁷ accompany a decrease in entropy due

to the immobilization of a large number of solvent molecules around the charged species. In the present case, as expected, we find a decrease in entropy all through for the process. The entropy change is practically constant upto 30%. The small change around 45-50% methanol may be the result of the difference in electrostatic effects on the process^{2a}. This possibly indicates that upto 30% methanol, the solvation of ions is by water molecules and beyond 30% (may be 50%^{2a}) methanol, methanol molecules start competing with water molecules in the primary solvation sphere. The enthalpy-change for the dissociation process also passes through a maximum around 30% methanol, substantiating our assumption. ΔC_p° for the dissociation process decreases with increase in the percentage of the organic component. Similar decrease has been observed in case of dissociation of formic, acetic and propionic acids in dioxane-water media^{2a}.

References

1. A. K. BASU and S. ADITYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 155.
2. A. K. BASU and S. ADITYA, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1978, **23**, 1941.
3. A. K. BASU and S. ADITYA, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1979, **24**, 275.
4. H. S. HARNED and G. L. KAZANJIAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 1912.
5. H. S. HARNED and L. D. FALLON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 2377.
6. H. S. HARNED, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1938, **43**, 275.
7. H. S. HARNED and R. W. EHLERS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 2379.
8. H. S. HARNED and T. R. DEDELL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 3308.
9. H. S. HARNED and N. D. EMBREE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **57**, 1669.
10. A. L. BACARELLA, E. GRUNWALD, H. P. MARSHALL and E. L. PURLEE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1955, **20**, 747.
11. T. SHEDLOVSKY and R. L. KAY, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1956, **60**, 151.
12. M. PAABO, R. A. ROBINSON and R. G. BATES, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1964, **9**, 374.
13. R. G. BATES, "Electrometric pH Determination: Theory and Practice", Wiley, New York, 1954, p. 204.
14. R. G. BATES, "Electrometric pH Determination: Theory and Practice", Wiley, New York, 1954, p. 112.
15. H. S. HARNED and R. W. EHLERS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 1350.
16. W. J. HAMER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **56**, 860.
17. C. W. DAVIES, H. W. JONES and C. B. MONK, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1952, **48**, 921.
18. V. S. K. NAIR and G. H. NANCOLLAS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 4144.
19. S. CHAKRABORTY and S. ADITYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 493.
20. H. S. HARNED and H. C. THOMAS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **57**, 1666.
21. S. L. MELTON and E. S. AMIS, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1968, **13**, 429.
22. R. A. ROBINSON and R. H. STOKES, "Electrolytic Solutions", 2nd ed., Butterworths, London, 1959, p. 470, 475.
23. F. A. LONG and W. F. McDEVITT, *Chem. Rev.*, 1952, **51**, 119.
24. H. S. HARNED and B. B. OWEN, "The Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions", 2nd ed., Reinhold, New York, p. 512.
25. H. S. HARNED and B. B. OWEN, "The Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions", 2nd ed., Reinhold, New York, p. 514.
26. S. K. PAL, U. C. BHATTACHARYYA, S. C. LAHIRI and S. ADITYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 497; S. C. LAHIRI and S. ADITYA, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1970, **244**, 351.
27. H. S. FRANK and M. EVANS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1945, **13**, 507.
28. M. PAABO, R. A. ROBINSON and R. G. BATES, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 415.